

Role of Big Data Analysis and Machine Learning in Ecommerce - Customer Segmentation

Alphy Mathew

PG Scholar
Master of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kottaym, India
alphyathew@mca.ajce.in

T J Jobin

Asst. Professor
Master of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kottaym, India
tjjobin@amaljyothi.ac.in

Abstract— In recent years, the e-commerce industry has placed a greater emphasis on big data analytics (BDA). The boom in online shopping will increase the opposition among various businesses within the e-commerce discipline. To enhance the commercial enterprise technique in e-commerce the agencies want to undertake business intelligence via big data analytics. The effect of big data analytics performs a critical position in e-commerce for the competitive commercial enterprise environment. Ecommerce corporations are finding methods to extract meaningful facts from large datasets in which statistics receives generated at a greater velocity, different variety, and at high volumes which might be regularly referred to as big data. Because of those traits, it is impossible to correctly control and examine big data using traditional databases.

Keywords E-commerce, big data analytics, dataset, statistics (key words)

I. INTRODUCTION

Big data permit e-trade groups to recognize clients higher through customer behavior analysis with big data analytics, e-trade groups can deliver enhanced shopping stories to their customers via faster shipment, greater personalized services, and better customer service. The use of big data for customer segmentation can provide different services of an excellent greater important variety. With the collected huge data, businesses can expect purchasing behaviors and determine which customers may be more likely to shop for a product at release.

One of the most important applications of unsupervised learning is customer segmentation. Companies can become aware of numerous categories of clients through clustering tactics, allowing them to target the ability consumer base. The K-means clustering algorithm is used here, which is the most important approach for clustering unlabeled datasets. Customer segmentation is the division of a customer base into various groups of people who share a similarity in various ways that can be used in advertising and marketing, such as gender, age, interests, and other spending habits. Customer segmentation is based on the idea that each customer has unique needs that require a tailored marketing strategy to address.

Companies want to gain a better understanding of the clients they're pursuing. As a result, their goal must be distinct, and it must be tailored to meet the objectives of each and every male and female client. Furthermore, by utilizing the data gathered, businesses can have a better understanding of customer possibilities as well as the requirements for locating valuable sectors that will yield the greatest profit. As a result, businesses

will be able to better strategize their advertising strategies and lessen the risk of their investment being jeopardized.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

This investigation will examine the various consequences of big data on the e-trade experience for each carrier and customers, i.e., clients, based on the linked research and reviews. The contemporary artwork will aid academics in improving BDA usage in e-commerce by assessing vendors' and clients' experiences.

As large information is been used in many sectors, it extensively affects E-commerce services and plays a main role in commercial enterprise making choices. The usage of massive records has pretty grown in e-commerce, many big retailers values this information's facts and helps them for predicting consumer pastimes and provide their clients relative and involved searches when they keep on their site, in order that they entice the purchaser by means of giving the required and relevant searches of the goods or objects. The usage of the related facts from this survey paper the researchers can provide you with applicable and tough structures to extending the advantages of massive statistics utilization closer to e-trade for each customer in addition to the retailers. In these competitive and speedy surroundings, customers, on the whole, go with online advertisements or via search engines like google and yahoo by means of lowering the inefficiency of the actual-time markets. Corporations can find their popularity to paintings on a selected product to develop with the opposition and can also without difficulty locate and examine with different online stores.

Big data analytics is progressively adding value to e-commerce organizations by converting information into insights for sound decision-making and solutions to business problems leveraging the dynamics of people, processes, and technology. This is a comprehensive approach that includes data, sources, skills, and processes to help you achieve a competitive advantage. Google, Amazon, ebay, ASOS, Netflix, and Facebook are among the major e-commerce companies that have already used BDA and seen significant growth. This study provides a valuable starting point for the application of BDA in rising e-commerce research through its systematic review and construction of a taxonomy of the essential features of BDA. The research proposes a strategy for encapsulating all of the beneficial behaviors that develop and shape BDA abilities. Similarly, the study finds that once BDA and its scope are well defined, different traits and types of big data are well understood, and challenges are properly addressed, the BDA software will maximize business value by facilitating

the widespread use and rapid dissemination of insights across organizations

In marketing, one manner to boom earnings is to speak with customers to determine consumer desires. The conversation is constructed in line with the traits of the customer. Communication may be very hard to create using personal tactics. So, it is necessary to divide customers into corporations that have the same characteristics, and that is known as client segmentation. Customer segmentation is the activity to categorize or to classify an item or situation to a collection that has been diagnosed to have in the commonplace. Customer Segmentation Intelligence to enhance advertising in presenting services or products that meet the desires of every customer group. Customer segmentation is a manner to enhance communication with the consumer, to recognize the wishes of the customer, consumer pastime so that appropriate verbal exchange may be constructed. Customer Segmentation had to get capability clients used to boom income. Capacity patron information can be used to offer service the traits of the client including e-commerce services as a media buying and selling online.

III. METHODOLOGY

The methods used in this study is described in this section.

Rstudio

Rstudio is an IDE (integrated development environment) for the R programming language. It features a terminal, syntax-highlighting editor, charting, history, debugging, and workspace control tools, as well as plotting, history, debugging, and workspace control tools.

The R Foundation for Statistical Computing supports R, a programming language and free software program environment for statistical computing and graphics. The R programming language is widely used by statisticians and data miners to create statistical tools and evaluate data.

Data set

CustomerID	Gender	Age	Annual.Inc.Spending Score (1-100)	
1	Male	19	39	
2	Male	21	15	81
3	Female	20	16	6
4	Female	23	16	77
5	Female	31	17	40
6	Female	22	17	76
7	Female	35	18	6
8	Female	23	18	94
9	Male	64	19	3
10	Female	30	19	72
11	Male	67	19	14
12	Female	35	19	99
13	Female	58	20	15
14	Female	24	20	77
15	Male	37	20	13
16	Male	22	20	79
17	Female	35	21	35
18	Male	20	21	66
19	Male	52	23	29
20	Female	35	23	98
21	Male	35	24	35
22	Male	25	24	73

A dataset is a collection of numerous pieces of facts known as variables (normally organized via columns). A variable could have one or several values (facts for one or several cases).

Comma Separated Values (CSV) stands for Comma Separated Values. These database fields were exported into a single-line arrangement in which each database document is separated by a comma. CSV files are basically plain text files with a different extension.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION

Step1: perform data exploration.

- Results from the data exploration degree offer insights into the suitability of different segmentation strategies for extracting marketplace segments.
- The different functions used to perform data exploration.
- Open rstudio and change the working directory. After that, import the necessary packages for this role and read the data.
- names() function used to display the column names and str() function used to display the structure of the dataset.
- Use the head() function to output a summary of the top six rows of the dataset, and the summary() features to output a summary of it.
- Here sd() function gives the standard deviation of each variable and the summary() function used to find the summary of each variable.

Code:

```
rm(list = ls())
setwd("D:/Rprogramming/Projects")
getwd()

#1.data exploration.
customer_data <- read.csv("Mall_Customers.csv",header = TRUE)
names(customer_data)
str(customer_data)
head(customer_data)
summary(customer_data$Age)
sd(customer_data$Age)
summary(customer_data$Annual.Income..k..)
sd(customer_data$Annual.Income..k..)
summary(customer_data$Spending.Score..1.100.)
sd(customer_data$Spending.Score..1.100.)
```

Output:

```
> rm(list = ls())
> setwd("D:/Rprogramming/Projects")
> getwd()
[1] "D:/Rprogramming/Projects"
> #1.data exploration.
> customer_data <- read.csv("Mall_Customers.csv",header = TRUE)
> names(customer_data)
[1] "CustomerID" "Gender" "Annual.Income..k.." "Spending.Score..1.100." "Age"
> str(customer_data)
'data.frame': 200 obs. of 5 variables:
 $ CustomerID : int 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 ...
 $ Gender : chr "Male" "Male" "Female" "Female" ...
 $ Age : int 19 21 20 23 31 22 35 23 64 30 ...
 $ Annual.Income..k.. : int 15 15 16 16 17 17 18 18 19 19 ...
 $ Spending.Score..1.100.: int 39 81 6 77 40 76 6 94 3 72 ...
> head(customer_data)
  CustomerID Gender Age Annual.Income..k.. Spending.Score..1.100.
1           1   Male  19              15                39
2           2   Male  21              15                81
3           3 Female  20              16                 6
4           4 Female  23              16                77
5           5 Female  31              17                40
6           6 Female  22              17                76
> summary(customer_data$Age)
   Min. 1st Qu.  Median    Mean 3rd Qu.    Max.
 18.00  28.75   36.00   38.85  49.00   70.00
> sd(customer_data$Age)
[1] 13.96901
> summary(customer_data$Annual.Income..k..)
   Min. 1st Qu.  Median    Mean 3rd Qu.    Max.
 15.00  41.50   61.50   60.56  78.00  137.00
> sd(customer_data$Annual.Income..k..)
[1] 26.26472
> summary(customer_data$Spending.Score..1.100.)
   Min. 1st Qu.  Median    Mean 3rd Qu.    Max.
  1.00  34.75   50.00   50.20  73.00   99.00
> |
```

Step 2: Second Customer Gender Visualization.

To display the gender distribution over the customer data dataset, make a barplot and a piechart.

Code:

```
#Customer Gender Visualization barplot and a piechart
a = table(customer_data$Gender)
barplot(a,main="Using BarPlot to display Gender Comparision",
        ylab="Count",
        xlab="Gender",
        col=rainbow(2),
        legend=rownames(a))
```

Output:

Observe that the number of females is more than the number of males in the barplot above.

Let's use a pie chart to depict the male-to-female distribution ratio.

Code:

```
pct=round(a/sum(a)*100)
lbs=paste(c("Female","Male")," ",pct,"%",sep=" ")
install.packages("plotrix")
library(plotrix)
pie3D(a,labels=lbs,
      main="Pie Chart Depicting Ratio of Female and Male")
```

Output:

Pie Chart Depicting Ratio of Female and Male

Conclusion: The percentage of females in the customer dataset is 56 percent, while the percentage of males is 44 percent, based on the graph above.

Step 3: Visualization of Age Distribution

Let's make a histogram and boxplot to see how the frequency of customer ages is distributed. To begin, make a summary of the Age variable.

Code:

```
summary(customer_data$Age)
hist(customer_data$Age,
      col="blue",
      main="Histogram to Show Count of Age Class",
      xlab="Age Class",
      ylab="Frequency",
      labels=TRUE)
boxplot(customer_data$Age,
        col="red",
        main="Boxplot for Descriptive Analysis of Age")
```

Output:

Boxplot for Descriptive Analysis of Age

We can deduct from the above two visualizations that the average consumer age is between 30 and 35. Customers must be at least 18 years old and no more than 70 years old.

Step 4: Analysis of the Annual Income of the Customers.

Develop graphics to analyze the customers' annual income the data will be examined using a density plot once a histogram has been plotted.

Code:

```
summary(customer_data$Annual.Income..k..)
hist(customer_data$Annual.Income..k..,
      col="#660033",
      main="Histogram for Annual Income",
      xlab="Annual Income Class",
      ylab="Frequency",
      labels=TRUE)
plot(density(customer_data$Annual.Income..k..),
      col="yellow",
      main="Density Plot for Annual Income",
      xlab="Annual Income Class",
      ylab="Density")
polygon(density(customer_data$Annual.Income..k..),
        col="#ccff66")
```

Output:

According to the preceding descriptive study, the clients' least yearly income is \$15 and their maximum annual income is \$137. In the histogram distribution, people with an average income of 70 have the highest frequency count. All of the clients have an average salary of \$60.56. The annual revenue has a normal distribution, as seen in the Kernel Density Plot shown above.

Step 5: examining the customer's spending score.

Create a Boxplot and Histogram

```
Code:
summary(customer_data$Spending.Score..1.100.)
boxplot(customer_data$Spending.Score..1.100.,
         horizontal=FALSE,
         col="#990000",
         main="BoxPlot for Descriptive Analysis of Spending Score")
hist(customer_data$Spending.Score..1.100.,
     main="Histogram for Spending Score",
     xlab="Spending Score Class",
     ylab="Frequency",
     col="#6600cc",
     labels=TRUE)
```

Output:

The average spending score is 50.20, with a minimum of 1 and a maximum of 99. The Spending Score Descriptive Analysis shows that the minimum is 1, the maximum is 99, and the average is 50.20. Customers in classes 40 and 50 have the greatest spending score of all the classes, according to the histogram.

The next stage is to use the k-means clustering algorithm, and the first step is to specify how many clusters (k) we want in the final result. The technique begins by randomly picking k objects from the dataset to act as the clusters' initial centers.

The Euclidean Distance between the item and the cluster mean is used to describe this centroid. This is the "cluster assignment" stage. After the assignment is finished, the set of rules calculates the new mean value of each cluster in the data. After the centers have been recalculated, the observations are reviewed to see if they point to a distinct cluster. The items are reassigned using the updated cluster mean. This repeats itself for multiple times until the cluster no longer changes.

K-means clustering in a nutshell.

- The number of clusters that must be created has been determined.
- At random, the algorithm selects k objects from the dataset. This object is the initial cluster or mean.
- The centroid that is closest to it receives a new observation. The Euclidean Geometry In this assignment, the distance between the object and the centroid is employed.
- K clusters in the data points calculate the revised mean values in all of the cluster's data points to update the centroid. The kth cluster's centroid has a length of p and contains the means of all variables for the observations in the kth cluster. The letter p stands for the number of variables.
- Iterative minimization of the total inside the sum of squares. When we reach maximum iteration through iterative minimization of the entire sum of the square, the assignment will stop wiggling. The maximum number of iterations in R is set to 10 by default.

Choosing the Best Clusters

The number of clusters to use must be given when working with clusters. Should employ as many clusters as feasible the best clusters can be determined in one of three ways.

- Elbow method

- Silhouette method
- Gap statistic

Elbow method

Cluster partitioning techniques like k-means have the goal of defining clusters with the least degree of intra-cluster variation.

Minimize($\sum W(C_k)$), $k=1 \dots k$

Intra-cluster variation is denoted by $W(C_k)$, and the k th cluster is denoted by C_k . The total intra-cluster variation can be used to determine the compactness of the clustering boundary.

As a result, the best clusters can be defined as follows: Calculate the clustering algorithm for a range of k values to begin. Changing the number of clusters in k from one to 10 does this. After that, the total intra-cluster sum of squares is computed (iss). The plot is then determined by the number of k clusters present. The needed number of clusters in the model is depicted in this graph.

Code:

```
install.packages("purrr")
library(purrr)
set.seed(123)
# function to calculate total intra-cluster sum of square
iss <- function(k) {
  kmeans(customer_data[,3:5],k,iter.max=100,nstart=100,algorithm="Lloyd")$tot.withinss
}

k.values <- 1:10
iss_values <- map_dbl(k.values, iss)

plot(k.values, iss_values,
     type="b", pch = 19, frame = FALSE,
     xlab="Number of clusters K",
     ylab="Total intra-clusters sum of squares")
```

Output:

Based on the accompanying graph, which appears at the bend in the elbow plot, 4 is the proper number of clusters.

Average Silhouette Method

The average silhouette approach can be used to judge the clustering process' quality. You can see how well the data object fits within the cluster this way. You have good clustering if the average silhouette width is large. The average silhouette method calculates the mean of silhouette observations for various k values. The average silhouette over significant values for k clusters can be maximized with the ideal number of k clusters.

Using the k-mean function and the silhouette function from the cluster package, we can compute the average silhouette width. The ideal cluster will have the highest average in this case.

Code:

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```
library(cluster)
library(gridExtra)
library(grid)
```

```
k2<-kmeans(customer_data[,3:5],2,iter.max=100,nstart=50,algorithm="Lloyd")
s2<-plot(silhouette(k2$cluster,dist(customer_data[,3:5],"euclidean")))
```

Output:

Code:

```
k3<-kmeans(customer_data[,3:5],3,iter.max=100,nstart=50,algorithm="Lloyd")
s3<-plot(silhouette(k3$cluster,dist(customer_data[,3:5],"euclidean")))
```

Output:

Code:

```
k4<-kmeans(customer_data[,3:5],4,iter.max=100,nstart=50,algorithm="Lloyd")
s4<-plot(silhouette(k4$cluster,dist(customer_data[,3:5],"euclidean")))
```

Output:

Code:

```
k5<-kmeans(customer_data[,3:5],5,iter.max=100,nstart=50,algorithm="Lloyd")
s5<-plot(silhouette(k5$cluster,dist(customer_data[,3:5],"euclidean")))
```

Output:

Code:

```
k6<-kmeans(customer_data[,3:5],6,iter.max=100,nstart=50,algorithm="Lloyd")
s6<-plot(silhouette(k6$cluster,dist(customer_data[,3:5],"euclidean")))
```

Output:

Code:

```
k7<-kmeans(customer_data[,3:5],7,iter.max=100,nstart=50,algorithm="Lloyd")
s7<-plot(silhouette(k7$cluster,dist(customer_data[,3:5],"euclidean")))
```

Output:

Code:

```
k8<-kmeans(customer_data[,3:5],8,iter.max=100,nstart=50,algorithm="Lloyd")
s8<-plot(silhouette(k8$cluster,dist(customer_data[,3:5],"euclidean")))
```

Output:

Code:

```
k9<-kmeans(customer_data[,3:5],9,iter.max=100,nstart=50,algorithm="Lloyd")
s9<-plot(silhouette(k9$cluster,dist(customer_data[,3:5],"euclidean")))
```

Output:

Code:

```
k10<-kmeans(customer_data[,3:5],10,iter.max=100,nstart=50,algorithm="Lloyd")
s10<-plot(silhouette(k10$cluster,dist(customer_data[,3:5],"euclidean")))
```

Output:


```
pcclust=prcomp(customer_data[,3:5],scale=FALSE) #principal component analysis
summary(pcclust)
pcclust$rotation[,1:2]
```

Output:

Importance of components:

	PC1	PC2	PC3
Standard deviation	26.4625	26.1597	12.9317
Proportion of Variance	0.4512	0.4410	0.1078
Cumulative Proportion	0.4512	0.8922	1.0000


```
> pcclust$rotation[,1:2]
```

	PC1	PC2
Age	0.1889742	-0.1309652
Annual.Income..k..	-0.5886410	-0.8083757
Spending.Score..1.100.	-0.7859965	0.5739136

Step 6: Model Visualization Using Annual Income and Spending Score.

Code:
set.seed(1)

```
ggplot(customer_data, aes(x=Annual.Income..k., y=Spending.Score..1.100.)) +
geom_point(stat="identity", aes(color=as.factor(k6$cluster))) +
scale_color_discrete(name="", breaks=c("1", "2", "3", "4", "5", "6"),
labels=c("Cluster 1", "Cluster 2", "Cluster 3", "Cluster 4", "Cluster 5", "Cluster 6"))
ggtitle("Segments of Mall Customers", subtitle="Using K-means Clustering")
```

Output:

We can see that there is a distribution of 6 clusters in the above graphic –

Clusters 6 and 4 — These clusters reflect customer data with a medium annual salary spend and a medium annual salary income.

Cluster 1 - Customers with a high annual income and a high annual spend make up this cluster.

Cluster 3 - Customers with a low yearly income and a low yearly income spend are represented in this cluster.

Cluster 2 - This cluster is characterized by a high annual income and a low annual outlay.

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Cluster 5 - People in this cluster have a low annual income but a high annual expenditure.

Step 7: Model Visualization Using Annual Income and Age. Code:

```
ggplot(customer_data, aes(x=Spending.Score..1.100., y=Age)) +
geom_point(stat="identity", aes(color=as.factor(k6$cluster))) +
scale_color_discrete(name="",
breaks=c("1", "2", "3", "4", "5", "6"),
labels=c("Cluster 1", "Cluster 2", "Cluster 3", "Cluster 4", "Cluster 5", "Cluster 6")) +
ggtitle("Segments of Mall Customers", subtitle="Using K-means Clustering")
```

Output:

Code:

```
kcols=function(vec){cols=rainbow(length(unique(vec)))
return(cols[as.numeric(as.factor(vec))])}
digCluster<-k6$cluster; dignm<-as.character(digCluster); # K-means clusters
plot(pcclust$x[,1:2], col=kcols(digCluster),pch=19,xlab="K-means",ylab="classes")
legend("bottomleft",unique(dignm),fill=unique(kcols(digCluster)))
```

Output

RESULT

Analysis of customer segmentation.

Customers with a medium pca1 and medium pca2 score make up clusters 4 and 1.

Cluster 6 -this cluster represents customers with a high pca2 and a low pca1.

Cluster 5 is made up of customers that have a medium pca1 score but a poor pca2 score.

Cluster 3 is made up of customers with a high pca1 and pca2 income. Clients in cluster 2 have a high pca2 but a moderate annual income spending.

V. CONCLUSION

The customer segmentation model was created using unsupervised learning, a type of machine learning. We used a clustering approach called K-means clustering in particular. After analyzing and visualizing the data, we implemented the algorithm.

Clustering allows us to have a better understanding of the factors, allowing us to make more informed decisions. Companies can produce products and services that target clients based on many characteristics such as income, age, spending patterns, and so on, once customers have been identified. More

sophisticated patterns, such as product reviews, are also taken into account for improved categorization.

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